

THE SPECIFIC IMPORTANCE OF USING THE FOLK METHOD IN THE PRESERVATION OF LATE RIPENING APPLE HARVEST

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Abstract: This article describes the technology of long-term storage of late-ripening apples using the folk method.

Key words: storage, temperature, light, humidity, environment, temperate, weather.

Enter. Consistent economic reforms in the agricultural sector of our country are aimed at fully satisfying the population's demand for quality food products and fundamentally improving the supply in this area to global standards.

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 "On approval of the strategy for the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030" No. PF-5853, development of agriculture, including horticulture roadmaps for increasing the production, improving the quality, processing and storage of products to world standards, and increasing the export value of products were developed.

If we pay attention to the results of the conducted research, it is emphasized that apple is the most cultivated, most consumed and most useful fruit for the human body. More than 1700 different varieties of apples are cultivated and cultivated in our country. We grow early-ripening, mid-ripening and late-ripening apple varieties according to the period of ripening. In order to continuously provide the population's consumption needs for wet apples throughout the year, it is possible to preserve them for consumption based on various folk methods and various storage technologies in modern refrigerated warehouses. It is desirable to store apples mainly from mid-ripe and late-ripe apples. From the high price of the realized fruit, its growing and storing entities achieve significant economic efficiency.

In order to continuously provide the population of our republic with food products, to fill the domestic market with high-quality fruit and vegetable and viticulture products, further development of fruit and vegetable growing and viticulture, which is one of the leading sectors in the agro-industrial complex, is of great importance. Because this sector provides an opportunity to continuously meet the demand of the population for quality food products and industrial enterprises for raw materials. In addition, Uzbekistan is a country with a high potential for the production of horticultural and viticultural products. For this reason, in order to develop the industry, special attention is being paid to the issues of stable supply of food products to the population in our country, and the full satisfaction of consumer demand at the expense of domestically grown fruit and vegetable, apple, grape and potato products.

Main part:

One of the common ways of storing apples in Tashkent region is storage in sand.

For this, the bottom of the box is sprinkled with river sand in a thin (3-4 cm) thickness, then a row of apples is picked, and then it is done.

The sand should be clean of soil and other objects and dried to a moisture content of 30 percent. In this way, apples are stored until March.

Sometimes small wood shavings and shavings are used for storage. Their humidity should not be higher than 12 percent. High moisture content must be dried.

First, a piece of paper is written on the bottom of the box, then a layer of rice paper is placed, and a number of fruits are picked, and so on.

After the box is full, another layer of pierah is placed on it, and it is covered with paper. In this case, the fruits can be stored from the end of January to the beginning of February.

In some districts of Samarkand region, it is used to store apples in ditches that are periodically watered.

For this purpose, a trench with a depth of 0.5-1 meter, a width of 0.7-0.8 meters, and an arbitrary length is dug in one direction.

A ditch with a depth of 20-25 centimeters in length and a width of 20-25 centimeters is dug, and a 1-1.5-meter diameter 0.5-0.6-meter fence is dug at the end of the trenches for water to flow.

Before placing the apples, a mat woven from vine rust is placed at the bottom of the trench and straw is written on it, and then the fruits are picked.

The pile of apples stored in the trench is 0.4-0.5 meters high, and rice straw is pressed on top of it with a thickness of 40-50 centimeters.

During the 1-2 weeks of the fruit storage period, kunora is sprinkled at the rate of 0.3-0.4 m³ of water per ton. During this period, the fruits cool down and the microorganisms present in them and most of the impurities are washed away.

After that, water is poured every week and more often. In winter, straw is covered over the trench with a thickness of 30-40 centimeters. On hot days (October, November, March, April), the trench is covered with a covering to prevent direct sunlight. During the storage process, some areas of the trench are opened for inspection and the condition of the fruits is monitored.

Storage of apples in packages. This method is used in farms in Samarkand, Favgana and Tashkent regions. Sizot waters are excavated at a depth of 2.0-2.5 meters in the areas where the sizot is located, sand is placed at the bottom and it is placed in a row with a layer of fruits.

It is well closed so that moisture does not get inside.

For ventilation, a chimney is placed around the fence.

Temperature and air humidity are controlled by means of various moisture absorbers and by opening and closing the chimney.

Sometimes dried mint on shelves and boxes is wrapped against fungal diseases. Put basil or garlic pieces. This makes it possible to store fruits until March and April.

Mode and conditions of storage of apples. Varieties of seeded fruits are unique in terms of sorting, often for apples or pears, a separate storage plan is recommended. A good temperature of 0Q10C can be used to store seeded fruits. But for unripe varieties, they will not fully ripen when stored at such a temperature. That is, it preserves maturation activity, color. The taste and aroma will not be good. In addition, the fruits of some varieties lose the characteristic of full ripening as a result of long storage at 00C, as a result, darkening of the skin and flesh increases.

On the other hand, "Baikal", "White Rosemary", "Golden Delishes" varieties withstand -1.50C overcooling and maintain their consumption qualities with a gradual increase in temperature.

Apples are resistant to extreme cold conditions and can be cooled at the same time. In sharp cooling and high temperature, the effect of shearing increases.

X. Ch. According to Boriev et al. [2002], it is difficult to keep the storage temperature in the required form in large refrigerating warehouses. Because of this, the temperature may drop by 1-1.50C and the fruits may die. Fruits stored in refrigerators should be warmed gradually. When storing fruits with seeds, it is recommended to keep the relative humidity of the air in the range of 90-95 percent.

The diversity of the apple variety makes it more difficult to store it. Because each variety requires a specific storage procedure. Therefore, the storage efficiency of apples is increased if they are of the same variety or of the same type. Apples should be inspected during storage. The boxes where the apples are placed are monitored once or twice a month. If there is a defect in the stored apples, they are again divided into varieties [Trisvyatsky L.A., Lesik B.V., Kurtina V.N., 1991].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Analytical study of the characteristics of a number of apple varieties recommended for long-term storage of apples, storage technologies. We will also be able to make conclusions and suggestions based on the results of our observation of apple harvest storage in different environments.

1. The main opportunity to provide the population with wet fruit for a long time is the localization of the most productive varieties of late-ripening apple varieties and the creation of new varieties.
2. When apples are stored in a natural environment with an air temperature of 1-40C and a humidity of 90%, the content of vitamin C and Fe is stored even more.
3. It is possible to further improve the population's need for wet fruit by establishing home storage of apples in every household with high-quality storage.
4. To create technologies without the least losses by carrying out research and research on the further improvement of the methods of high-quality storage of apples for a long period of time.

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